

A Study On Digital Marketing And Digital Marketing Channels

Paper Id : 19172 Submission Date : 2024-08-09 Acceptance Date : 2024-08-18 Publication Date : 2024-08-20
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13349006

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Deepika Singh

Research Scholar
Department Of Commerce
MMH College
Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India,

Abhishek Kumar Singh

Assistant Professor
Department Of Commerce
MMH College
Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Inamur Rahaman

Assistant Professor
Department Of Commerce
MMH College
Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Digital marketing is the most used type of marketing in today's time, it not only benefits the company but is also very helpful for the consumers. Digital marketing is a type of marketing in which products and services are promoted and sold through digital mediums, which includes internet, mobile devices, and social media. The founder of digital marketing is Philip Kotler and digital marketing started in 1990. Digital marketing is also called online marketing, web marketing or internet marketing. Digital marketing is mostly used to attract new customers, promote the brand and increase sales. This study was done with the help of secondary data. A lot of literature and web sources were used in it for a deep study of the types of digital marketing or digital marketing channels and benefits. Research papers, newspapers, articles, websites, case studies and reports have been used. The purpose of writing this paper is to understand digital marketing and digital marketing channels and benefits.

Keywords Digital Marketing , E-mail Marketing, Affiliate marketing, SEO

Introduction In today's time the use of internet has increased, everything has become digital, with the increasing use of internet, nowadays companies have also started promoting their brands through digital medium so that maximum number of people can be attracted for their products. In the earlier times when things were not digitized, companies used traditional marketing for selling and promoting their products which included television, newspapers, billboards, door to door selling, magazines, cinema halls etc. Marketing includes targeting a specific group, creating, promoting, and distributing products or services. Marketing's primary goal is to enhance recognition and interest in a company's products or services, draw in potential clients, and ultimately drive sales and profits. It is a crucial component of every business strategy and centers around innovative planning and strategies to connect with and captivate the target audience. Digital marketing involves using digital channels, platforms, and technologies to promote products or services as a specialized marketing strategy. It uses online resources and digital advertising to reach out to potential clients and build connections with them. The extensive utilization of the internet and the quick growth of online platforms and social media have led to the rising visibility and effectiveness of digital marketing. Digital marketing provides businesses with multiple resources and analytics to track their campaigns' performance, reach desired audiences, and tweak strategies in response to real-time feedback. Compared to traditional marketing methods, it offers less reach, availability, and interaction, which is why it is a vital element of modern marketing strategies.

Digital Marketing refers to advertising products or services using various online platforms. In a straightforward manner, digital marketing involves reaching out to customers through various online platforms. The key components are SEO, email marketing, social media tactics, and PPC advertising. Key components of internet marketing are organic search, mobile optimization, content marketing, social media strategy, and email campaigns. Combining these elements will result in strong digital marketing campaigns. Therefore Traditional Marketing and Digital Marketing are two separate approaches to marketing both aimed at promoting products and services and connecting with the target audience. Traditional Marketing uses traditional methods to promote products and services, whereas Digital Marketing uses digital platforms and technologies for the same objective.

<https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-global-overview-report>

Objective of study

1. To Study Digital marketing and Digital marketing channels.
2. To Study the benefits of Digital marketing for customers.
3. To Study difference between Traditional marketing and Digital marketing.

Review of Literature

Numerous research papers and articles offer in-depth information on Digital marketing. The results of the literature review are provided below:

Harshit Sharma (2023) Says Digital marketing has a major influence on consumer behavior and is more powerful than traditional marketing in the current digital era. Customers are purchasing goods and services. More inclined to be impacted by online advertising compared to offline advertising, especially in terms of buying choices. of technology has significantly increased in recent years. The utilization of social media and mobile devices is becoming more and more crucial for marketers to connect with their desired audience and impact their actions. The number of years lived Consumers' perception and behavior towards digital marketing are greatly influenced by their gender and age. Employing various promotional techniques and strategies utilizing multiple marketing channels is more efficient than depending on just one marketing strategy.

Danish and Bhola Dutt Tiwari et.al (2023) The main findings of this research show that the digital marketing sector has made a strong impact on the Indian market and is expected to expand rapidly in the coming years. One important aspect of this study is that it greatly aids in understanding the perspectives of marketing managers. Moving in the direction of utilizing digital marketing tactics. This study also suggests opportunities for further research that could explore carrying out the Empirical research is conducted to understand how bosses, CEOs, and other managers perceive the future importance of digital marketing. The growth of this trend will be supported by technology, without leading to technology fatigue that could impact business operations and income .The results of the study indicate that conducting empirical research is necessary to improve the understanding and support of the digital marketing sector continuing growth in India. This study should also consider the views of marketing professionals.

Manasmita Panda and Aishwarya Mishra (2022) This paper discovered that the critical aspect of digital marketing is the most essential. The key is to engage with the users. The ladder of engagement has demonstrated different strategies for engaging connect with the clients. The research has also shown that to make use of the digital technology In order to market effectively, companies must create an efficient platform. It needs to be repaired. Research has demonstrated that integrating all systems has become crucial in the present situation. with the digital platform's. The shift of newspapers from print to digital format .The online edition has demonstrated the latest digitalization trends. The text should be paraphrased using the same input language and keeping the same number of words. Advances in technology are enhancing the research and implementation of digital marketing. Mr. Pooran Singh and Dr. Jitendra (2021) Narrated the Since its inception, the digital advertising ecosystem has had to address numerous issues such as spam, ad fraud, and cyber security concerns in order to operate and expand. A new trend, ad blocking, has been included in the lineup. In a brief span of time, this problem has become significant and continues to expand as it enters the domain of mobile devices and proliferates within them.

Neha Sharma (2021) Ensure their message is reaching the right audience and resonating with them effectively. Achieve success and be financially successful. Digital advertising enables improved business expansion .Brands nowadays are able to quickly become well-known and increase in popularity in a short amount of time. Also lead to negative consequences if not managed properly. Backfire with twice the strength. Modern individuals have no patience for irrationality .or irrelevant material and are very outspoken about it too. Everyone is affected, and Big brands no longer have the power to control the terms as they once did. Businesses may reach millions of individuals and explore on a large scale via digital platforms, but like with anything, this requires a solid marketing plan to get off the ground.

Ravi Shukla (2021) discuss in this paper, In India, there is a notable move towards digitalization taking place. During our research, we discovered that utilizing digital marketing strategies like SEO, SEM, campaign marketing, social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail marketing, display ads, e-books, optical discs, and games can greatly help businesses. Digital marketing is more cost-effective and efficient, and it generates a substantial business influence. Small businesses can now target particular consumers at a reduced price and compete fairly with bigger companies.

Mustafa Shuaieb Sabri (2021) The study revealed that India is not under constant surveillance; the fundamental rights of privacy and freedom of speech and expression should not be regulated illegally or in violation of the constitution. Given that the Constitutions have set constraints on speech and expression, it is important to maintain equilibrium. Large technology companies that own social platforms have the ability to moderate content and influence democracy. They and every individual need to be held accountable for their actions that have significant societal effect. The benefits of social media marketing are clear: it builds strong brand loyalty and closes the communication gap between companies and customers. It serves as an innovative marketing strategy to connect the company with a growing number of customers. It is also economically efficient, meaning large amounts of social media marketing funds are not necessary.

Dr. Madhu Bala and Mr. Deepak Verma (2018) In this research paper, we recognized the advantages that businesses can gain from utilizing Digital marketing. Optimizing websites for search engines, marketing in search engines, marketing through content. Marketing strategies that involve leveraging influential individuals, automating content creation, promoting products online, running specific promotional campaigns, and advertising. Marketing through social media, optimizing social media presence, direct marketing via email, advertising through display platforms. The use of e-books, optical disks, and games is becoming increasingly popular as technology advances.

Nivedita Jha and Namita Rani Behera and Manjunath (2016) discuss in this paper the advantages and functionalities of digital marketing. The given text should be provided in order to create a paraphrased version with the same input language and word count. reviews offer a perspective to assess the trends in digital marketing strategies noticed by clients. Consumers have a constant desire to purchase new products, even when not necessary. changes in the socio-economic landscape, such as a growing number of nuclear families andthus generates additional necessity. In order to survive in the market, marketers must adapt .Recognize and create fresh products as time goes on. The study

also discusses the significance of selecting effective tactics to maintain their market position in a highly competitive environment.

Methodology This study has been done with the help of secondary data so that you can get deep knowledge of digital marketing. For this, reports, research papers, articles, newspaper articles, websites, case studies have been used. The purpose of writing this paper is to give complete understanding of digital marketing and digital marketing channels and its benefits for the customers.

Analysis

Comparision Between Tradtional And Digital Marketing

Traditional marketing and digital marketing are two different marketing strategies that help businesses to promote their products and services.

What Is Traditional Marketing?

Traditional marketing is a type of marketing in which you can reach your target audience by using conventional methods to promote your goods or services, such as radio, print, television, direct mail, billboards, etc.

<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/traditional-marketing-meaning-importance-channels-advantages-and-disadvantages/>

What Is Digital Marketing?

Digital marketing is a marketing approach that reaches the target audience using online platforms and digital technology to promote their products and services such as mobile marketing, internet marketing, websites, social media, search engines, online ads, email marketing, affiliate marketing content marketing, etc.

<https://www.naukri.com/code360/library/difference-between-traditional-marketing-and-digital-market>

Difference between Traditional Marketing and Digital Marketing

Basis	Traditional Marketing	Digital Marketing
Definition	Traditional marketing is a type of marketing in which you can reach your target audience by using conventional methods to promote your goods or services, such as radio,	Digital marketing is a marketing approach that reaches the target audience using online platforms and digital technology to promote their products and services such as
	print, television, direct mail, billboards, etc.	mobile marketing, internet marketing, websites, social media, search engines, online ads, email marketing, affiliate marketing, content marketing, etc.
Meaning	In traditional marketing, conventional methods are used to promote products and services like TV advertisements, radio, print media, etc.	Digital marketing is the use of digital technology to promote products and services such as mobile, internet, email, online ads etc.
Communication method	One way communication use	Two way communication use
Range	Limited Range	Wide Range
Offline Channel/Online Channels	Traditional marketing uses offline channels such as TV, billboards, print, magazines etc.	Digital channels are used in digital marketing such as online marketing, email marketing, social media marketing, affiliate marketing etc.
Materials	Traditional marketing uses	Digital marketing uses multimedia

	tangible materials to promote products and services such as posters, flyers, brochures etc.	material such as images, videos, infographics to promote your products and services
Targeting	Standardized	Customized
Tracking	Not possible	Possible
Tweaking	Not possible once the advertisement is placed	One can change or edit anytime
Results	Slow results	Quick and live results
Cost	Traditional Marketing cost is very high.	Digital Marketing cost is low.

<https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-global-overview-report>

Benefits Of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a very popular way due to increasing use of internet day by day. Digital marketing is a powerful tool for promoting and selling your products and services in which customers are attracted by using digital technology.

There are many benefits of digital marketing:

Global Reach: In traditional marketing, there are a lot of restrictions regarding geographic area due to which the customer could not be reached properly but digital marketing strategy helps a lot in helping businesses to increase their products and services globally such that the customer reach increases. Digital marketing opens up growth opportunities so that businesses can explore themselves as much as possible

Easy to Learn: Brand awareness is one of the most significant advantage in digital marketing, especially for new businesses. Social media marketing helps businesses to promote their products or services on digital platforms like Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn they collaborate with other brands to spread awareness about their products.

Brand Building: Digital marketing allows two-way communication with your targeted audience in which you can interact with the audience, you can make them aware about your product, you can build a relationship with the audience which creates brand loyalty.

Measureability : In traditional marketing, it was very difficult to track any campaign or measure it in real time, but in digital marketing, we can see the performance of the campaign and can make our campaign better by measuring it. Digital marketing helps us to

create a correct strategy so that we can make people aware of our product through any campaign

Cost effective: Digital marketing campaign costs much less than traditional marketing. Traditional marketing campaigns used to cost a lot like printing banners, ad cost, printing cost etc. Digital marketing tool is a cost effective tool which can reach the world at a very low cost.

Effective Targeting: Effective targeting can be done through digital marketing, in this it becomes easy to promote your brand to a targeted audience, whereas it was a bit difficult to do so in traditional marketing, that is why digital marketing helps a lot to any company in making its brand reach its targeted audience.

Real Time Marketing: Digital platforms provide instant feedback whereas in traditional marketing it was very difficult to measure instant feedback. Digital platforms are open 24*7, consumers can easily check the details of their products and send their feedback.

TYPES OF DIGITAL MARKETING

E-mail Marketing: E-mail marketing is one of the best methods of digital marketing. E-mail is used in e-mail marketing to communicate and promote products and services. A large audience can be easily reached through it. There are many ways to send emails in e-mail marketing. This can be done like follow up emails, royalty program, special promotional offers, welcome email. Businesses can use email marketing to provide updates on products or services to clients.

SEO: The full name of SEO is search engine optimization. SEO is such a technique which helps any website to rank higher in the search engine. When any company uses the SEO technique in the articles of its website, it brings traffic to the company's website which helps the company's website to rank higher in the search engine. There are many search engines in the world like Google, Yahoo, Bing, Baidu, Ask.com, Duck Duck go.

Content Marketing: Content marketing is a digital marketing strategy that involves creating and sharing valuable information and relevant content that attracts people and engages the target audience. Content marketing including blog posts, articles, videos, infographics, e books, entertainment, webinars.

Affiliate Marketing: Affiliate marketing is a type of marketing in which a company compensates third person partners to promote the company's products and services.

Influencer Marketing: Influencer marketing is a type of social media in which influencers collaborate with a company to spread awareness of a company's products or services to a targeted audience. An influencer is a celebrity, public figure or content creator with an organic and engaged audience.

Video Marketing: Video marketing is a type of marketing in which a company promotes its products and services using video content to increase engagement through digital and social channels and educate consumers and customers about products and services so that it can easily reach its target audience. Video marketing is a powerful tool that easily connects businesses with their target audience through emotional content like funny, shocking or inspirational videos.

Organic Marketing: Organic marketing entails using digital methods to drive traffic to your website without relying on paid advertising. The goal is to increase brand recognition, drive traffic to landing pages and websites, establish connections, and create fresh leads by providing informative and valuable content.

Mobile Marketing: Mobile marketing involves promoting products and services through mobile devices like tablets and smartphones. Utilizing modern mobile technology features, such as location services, to customize marketing campaigns according to a person's whereabouts. Mobile marketing involves using technology to deliver personalized promotions of products or services to users who are always connected to a network.

Conclusion

Nowadays, due to increased internet usage, people are using social media on a daily basis. Today because of increasing number of internet users, companies are leaving traditional marketing and moving towards digital marketing. In today's time, digital marketing plays an important role. In digital marketing, products and services of any company are promoted through digital medium like e-mail marketing, affiliate marketing, mobile marketing, SEO etc. Due to excessive use of social media and internet, nowadays the use of traditional marketing has reduced significantly and companies have started using digital platforms and digital marketing so that they can easily promote their products and services. Digital marketing is better than traditional marketing and is also affordable. Digital marketing plays an important role for both businesses and consumers. Digital marketing increases both the growth and sales of any company. Digital marketing helps in promoting the brand of any company and reaching a targeted audience.

By seeing the growth of digital marketing, it becomes clear how helpful digital marketing is for people, it helps in the growth of business, it helps in increasing the sales of business. Internet usage is increasing a lot due to which every field is becoming digital, hence marketing has also become digital using which companies are earning very good profit. In the coming time, internet usage will increase further due to which digital marketing is a very good platform. To promote the brand of any company, I would say that without digital marketing the company cannot survive in the market, neither can it spread awareness about its brand, nor can it interact with people. Company growth is not possible without digital marketing, therefore digital marketing is a very good tool of marketing. In the coming time, digital marketing will completely replace traditional marketing. Digital marketing is a very effective tool that is affordable, flexible, and engaging than traditional marketing.

References

1. Anurag, U., & Kaur, S. (n.d.). *SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON DIGITAL MARKETING IN INDIA: PRESENT SCENARIO*. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3993539>
2. Bala, M., & Deepak Verma, M. (2018a). *A Critical Review of Digital Marketing Paper Type:- Review and Viewpoint*. *International Journal of Management*,
3. Basimakopoulou, M., Theologou, K., & Tzavaras, P. (2022). *A Literature Review on Digital Marketing: The Evolution of a Revolution*. *Journal of Social Media Marketing*, 1(1), 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.33422/jsmm.v1i1.901>
4. <http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,
5. <http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,<http://www.ijmra.us>,
6. Das, S. K., Gouri, D., & Lall, S. (2016). *Impact Factor: RJIF 5.22* www.managejournal.com Volume 2; Issue 8. *In International Journal of Commerce and Management Research*. www.managejournal.com *Digital-Marketing-A-Review*. (n.d.).
7. Dutt Tiwari, B., Rana, A., Professor, A., & professor, A. (2023). *A Study on Digital Marketing in India-it's Scope, Growth and Development*. *In International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews* www.ijrpr.com (Vol. 4). www.ijrpr.com